

PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF SOCIO-CULTURAL MANAGEMENT

Socio-Cultural Management Journal

Volume 4 (2021), Number 1, pp. 125-142

doi: <https://doi.org/10.31866/2709-846x.1.2021.235711>

p-ISSN 2709-846X, e-ISSN 2709-9571

Original Research Article

© O. Boyko, A. Jeremus-Lewandowska,

L. Otroshchenko, T. Povalii,

Yu. Baidak, 2021

UDC: 316.7-057.17:005.963.1

JEL Classification: M10, M12, M14, Z11

Received: 02/03/2021

**Olga Boyko¹, Anna Jeremus-Lewandowska²,
Larysa Otroshchenko¹, Tatiana Povalii¹, Yuliia Baidak³**

¹ Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine

² Ignacy Jan Paderewski Academy of Music in Poznan, Poznan, Poland

³ Sumy Regional Institute Postgraduate Pedagogical Education, Sumy, Ukraine

Situational Tasks Usage in the Professional Training of Socio-Cultural Activity Managers

Abstract: *Introduction.* Cultural and creative industries play an essential role in the modern economy. That is why the question of socio-cultural sphere management has become very significant. Due to the manager's involvement in this process, whose activity content is in managing and expanding cultural values and cultural product production, there is a necessity for innovative methods identification in socio-cultural activity managers' professional training. *Purpose and methods.* In the research process, general scientific methods as analysis, synthesis, systematization, and generalization of theoretical principles have been used, as well as specific scientific methods of terminological analysis, retrospective, biographical, comparison, concretization and classification, and empirical methods of discussion and pedagogical observation. *Results.* The importance of situational tasks as a dominant organizational form of socio-cultural activity managers' training has been clarified. Topics of situational tasks have been developed, which have been formed in the blocks. Situational tasks types have been characterized: “on the mobile decision”, “on decision choice”, “on data analysis”, “example tasks”, “on justification”, “on abilities and skills formation”, “on argumentative decision”, “on decision taken analysis”, “on information search”, “on complication”, “on algorithm production” and “on foresight”. The structure and content of the situational task have been analyzed and recommended professional situations in management have been presented. *Conclusions.* The scientific novelty of obtained results is in the theoretical support of the situational tasks usage

necessity as an organizational form of problematic education in the training of managers, and practical value is in their competitiveness advancing.

Keywords: situational task, manager, socio-cultural activity, cognitive task, professional situations.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. One of the most urgent problems of modern higher education is students' professional competence forming. The main idea is that education should provide theoretical knowledge, form exact abilities and skills, and develop students' ability to apply them in specific professional situations and conditions. Accordingly, not only content but also methods of students' professional training should correspond to education aims and the character of future professional activity. Thus, future managers of socio-cultural activity professional training in the universities should create the basis for their professional knowledge forming and developing their professional thinking. These aims should define a teacher's choice of innovative methods and organizational forms of teaching.

In our opinion, problem-based learning refers to innovative educational methods as it contributes to creative thinking formation and development. It is intended to the students' mental actions strengthening through thinking activity. A teacher within problem-based learning needs to choose organizational forms, which are the most valuable for the students' future professional activity. These organizational forms should involve students' acquired knowledge and analytical work, and students' mental activity. Obviously, one of the organizational forms of problem-based learning during future managers of socio-cultural activity professional training is situational tasks.

We would like to point out that situational tasks allow evaluating students' level of knowledge and impose on them the necessity to find the decisions in a real situation, contributing to future specialists' professional independence. However, designing situational tasks that would facilitate the formation of definite thinking qualities is a complicated task. Its solving requires methodical knowledge suitable for educational process problems search and preparing future managers of socio-cultural activity to the independent work with information. Thus, we consider situational tasks as a principal organizational form of future managers of socio-cultural activity professional training due to their ability to reveal students' creative skills, participate in discussions, get consultations, and analyze and solve problems.

State study of the problem. Ukrainian and foreign scientists researched various areas concerning situational tasks usage in future specialists' professional training. Thus, sufficient attention has been paid lately to situational tasks usage rationality in the educational methods, which were proved in foreign scientists' works (Y.-M. Tsai et al. (2008), J. Dietrich et al. (2017) and others).

Philosophical apprehension of situational tasks was presented in the research of Ukrainian scientists of E. Reshetnyak (2016), M. Kuzko (2019), V. Liubarets (2019), V. Kravets (1996), L. Ilyushin (2006), S. Zhuikova (2016) and others.

Designing and implementing situational tasks in the educational process were described in the works of I. Zharavina (2014), N. Kasatkina (2017), O. Moskalenko et al. (2016), I. Osadchenko et al. (2013), V. Surovtseva (2016) and others.

Nevertheless, even in terms of such active research as for situational tasks usage in education, their implementation in the modern educational environment goes slowly due to imperfectness and insufficient awareness of this educational process intensification in the system of higher education.

Thus, scientists' research in pedagogics and educational methodology has shown that future specialists' competence can be formed with the help of situational task usage, which is specific situation description, more or less typical to the exact activity type. However, even in terms of active research as for situational tasks implementation and usage in the educational process, they are implemented very slowly due to the imperfection and insufficient recognition of the intensification necessity of this educational process in higher education.

Unresolved issues. Despite the interest in using the situational task in the professional education of future specialists (particularly managers of socio-cultural activity), which is growing, there is a lack of scientific materials concerning methodological, theoretical, and technological aspects of this subject. Thus, demand in high-quality training of future managers of socio-cultural activity, the necessity of their practical managerial abilities and skills formation, the importance of conditions creation for developing students' creative potential, and lack of scientific-methodical basis on this subject make this research up-to-date.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose and research tasks. One of the socio-cultural activity manager bachelor educational program requirements is implementing various pedagogical technologies usage in the educational process, which aims to form and develop students' professional-practical skills. The advantage of this edu-

educational process is students' motivation for dynamic actions, stimulation to mutual thoughts and ideas exchange, feedback support, etc. That is why practical lessons containing analysis, modeling, and forecasting specific situational tasks play an essential role in the professional training of future socio-cultural activity managers.

The aim of the article is theoretical analysis, systematization, and generalization of scientific research on the determination of situational tasks' usage peculiarities in the professional training of future socio-cultural activity managers.

For the achievement of the aim, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- to examine the history of situational tasks emerging and developing;
- to highlight situational tasks essence and the aim of their inclusion in the educational process;
- to reveal situational tasks classification;
- to analyze situational tasks structure and content;
- to propose situational tasks for the professional training of socio-cultural activity managers.

Methodology and methods. The methodological basis of the research is introduced by the systematic approach, which is used for the analysis of a socio-cultural activity manager as an integral personality, which has definite connections and components of the professional competence and provides an opportunity to investigate such an organizational form of the problem-based learning as situational tasks.

The historical approach allowed examining emerging and developing of the practical activity sphere. In terms of the historical approach, we used the comparative-historical method, with the help of which we investigated the similarity and difference of the notion "situational task" in different cultures and on the different stages of the educational process. With the help of the terminological approach, we carried out the description, analysis, and clarification of the terminological system, particularly the notion of "situational task".

The personal approach allowed focusing on the student as an active and creative personality during the pedagogical experiment. The activity-based approach allowed considering the results of the experiment in the frames of the development and changes.

The structural-functional approach helps distinguish the system (situational task) structural components and define their functions. This approach allows studying connections of the different components to distinguish among them essential and unessential, necessary and random ones.

We also used axiological and culturological approaches, according to which we have designed situational tasks and carried out a methodical experiment on the principles of correlation theory and practice and personality needs satisfaction.

While choosing materials in the process of situational tasks design, we followed the following principles: situational tasks were defined in the form of information; tasks reflect specifics of professional activity; real situations were introduced in the tasks, which motivated different emotions demonstration; students understood researched problems; different ways of solving situational tasks were proposed.

To achieve the tasks, we have used a set of methods: general scientific ones as analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, which allowed systematizing scientific literature and Ukrainian and foreign scientists' opinion on a practice-oriented approach in the future socio-cultural activity managers training. We have used the following specific scientific methods: terminological analysis for the definition of situational tasks; retrospective and biographical ones for the detection of the situational tasks emergence and development; comparison, concretization, and classification for the design of situational tasks; empirical ones – interview and pedagogical observation during meetings and distance communication with the students of “Management of socio-cultural activity” specialty to study the positive experience and information verification as for situational tasks usage in the professional training of socio-cultural managers training.

Information base. The obtained results are based on Ukrainian and foreign scientists' theoretical and methodological works in pedagogics, management, and socio-cultural activity. We also have information from the personal authors' observation, carried out while teaching professional-oriented disciplines in the specialty of “Management of socio-cultural activity” in Sumy State University.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The history of situational tasks emergence and development

Scientists consider situational task usage in specialist training as one of fundamental and exceptional knowledge integration directions. Situational tasks integration in the educational process content provides not only socio-cultural activity managers training improvement and their cognitive activity enhancing, but also forms the idea concerning peculiarities of their future profession, which methods and means implementation allows solving profe-

ssional tasks. That is why a situational assignment is a form of educational material content, with the help of which a teacher can design a creative situation. Students can deal with it with the help of obtained knowledge.

We want to highlight the history of situational tasks emergence and development. As a special educational form, situational tasks were firstly designed in 1859-1952 by a famous representative of philosophical direction “pragmatism” J. Dewey. He analyzed the existing American educational system and pointed out that it had been detached from life, abstract, and had had scholastic education. He proposed his variant of reformation. According to his concept, the central activity of students had to be practical situations' solving, namely life tasks (Kravets, 1996, pp. 63-64).

In his theory, J. Dewey paid much attention to the role of students in education and their interests enhancing it. On the other hand, he departed from the precise delineation of education content and separate subjects, did not recognize scientific approach importance, and brought down the educational process to the practical activity (Kravets, 1996, p. 69). That is why, after a period, this educational form was criticized, and they refused it. Despite this, the pedagogical concept of J. Dewey greatly influenced the general character of school education of some countries and found its realization in the method of projects designed by J. Dewey follower, W. Kilpatrick. It is worth pointing out that J. Dewey and W. Kilpatrick's ideas were not completely rejected. They were adjusted and renewed in the USA and other countries through situational method usage in some disciplines teaching (that is, educational content was clearly defined).

3.2. Situational tasks essence and the aim of their integration in the educational process

Scientists interpret the notion of “situational task” differently. Thus, *S. Zhuikova* (2016) defines “situational task” as one of the technologies, allowing to achieve universal educational actions (personal, double subject) and subject results as well (p. 235).

S. Maglysh et al. (2017) think that situational task should be defined as a task that allows a student to master intellectual operations progressively in the process of work with the information: introduction → understanding → analysis → synthesis → implementation → evaluation. In their opinion, these tasks allow to not only evaluate how well students acquired educational material but make them look for solutions in the real situation, which contributes to the development of the professional independence of future doctors (p. 567).

In the *National pedagogical encyclopedia* (n.d.), “situational task” is defined as an educational task formulated in terms and conditions of a specific situation, with which the student comes across in practice. According to the definition of Ukrainian scientists: *O. Moskalenko et al.* (2016), “situational task” is a “fixed educational model-problem, in the process of interactive work with which the conditions for formation, development, and self-development of student’s personality as a future specialist are created” (pp. 349-350). In particular, *N. Kasatkina* (2017) describes the notion “situational task” as a mean of education and assessment, which includes a set of terms, aimed at the solving of a practically important situation to acquire educational subject content (p. 60).

Thus, in the context of the research, we define “situational task” as an educational task, with the help of which future managers of socio-cultural activity can see themselves in the role of employees and get minimal experience in finding reasonable solutions. Such an approach will help students to feel confident in similar real situations.

We want to formulate the aim of situational tasks integration in the educational process of future socio-cultural activity managers. Thus, the aim is in teaching students to select information, to sort it for solving specific task, to determine key problems, to search for alternative ways of solutions and assess them, to choose the optimal solution, and to form an actions program (*Surovtseva*, 2016, p. 48); to activate students’ social position, to contribute to stress tolerance, ability to respond to social changes challenges; to enable students to master obtained knowledge, to adjust abilities and skills (*Zharavina*, 2014, p. 957).

3.3. Situational tasks classification

We would like to examine the classification of situational tasks types, which is not perfect due to the variety of notion definitions. In our opinion, the best review of situational tasks is introduced in the scientific research of *I. Osadchenko et al.* (2014), who united them according to certain features (pp. 447-449):

- 1) tasks “on the mobile decision”, which contribute to fast problems solving skills formation;
- 2) tasks “on decision choice”, which aim is to choose unified exact solution among various variants: right and wrong ones;
- 3) tasks “on data analysis”, in which simple tasks become complicated due to extra information;
- 4) situational “example tasks”, aimed at theoretical material illustration;

5) tasks “on justification”, in the structure of which there is not only a situation itself but proposed variants of its solutions, which should be analyzed and argued;

6) tasks “on abilities and skills formation”, tasks that need step-by-step solving and reasoning with the help of students' obtained theoretical knowledge;

7) tasks “on the argumentative decision”, in which students are proposed to design two different of one situation with the following analysis of their thoughts concerning the situation;

8) tasks “on the decision taken analysis”, during which solving students either prove or disapprove proposed variants;

9) tasks “on information search”, in the structure of which information is presented partially, and students need to analyze additional sources individually;

10) tasks “on complication”, the aim of which is the introduction of additional conditions by a teacher after students have already presented possible solutions and they have to adjust the answer;

11) tasks “on algorithm production” which make students present stages of problem solving individually;

12) tasks “on foresight”, in which students need to design situations consequences.

We would like to emphasize that it is worth using all mentioned above situational tasks during socio-cultural activity managers' professional training. It helps to master different thematic blocks of professional information, to engage every student in specialized tasks performed in the exact type of activity, to choose various alternatives, to see a range of possible solutions variants, to forecast choice consequences of this or that variant, to experiment, to make a hypothesis, to find proofs, etc. It is also necessary to point out that this classification is very detailed, and for the most effective teaching of the socio-cultural activity managers, we should combine different types of situational tasks. Thus, tasks “on abilities and skills formation” can contain some elements of such tasks as “on data analysis”, “on information search”, “on algorithm production”, and so on.

3.4. Structure and content of situational tasks

Let us analyze situational task structure. Despite the variety of situational tasks, they have typical structure, which includes the name (preferably colorful one to attract attention); situation (event, problem, real-life story); personally significant cognitive task (practice-oriented content); information on the task

(presented in the form of the text, table, graphics, statistical data); tasks on the work with the information (Kasatkina, 2017; Ilyushin, 2006; Pavlenko, 2012).

Thus, during the situational task planning and preparing, a teacher tries to organize it so that students get not only knowledge but also develop skills and abilities to solve production and management tasks. All teacher's tasks and actions are directed on creating such circumstances that students can enhance their professional competence.

We would like to analyze situational task content, which is in-group discussion and in analyzing different professionally-oriented situations. It is worth pointing out that situational task content can be purposeful, or it can appear spontaneously. Thus, *O. Akulova et al.* (2008) state that there are different approaches to the situational tasks content design, and namely: the first approach – building tasks based on corresponding educational program issues; the second approach is based on the earlier accented types of practically oriented tasks, which every student needs to be able to solve; the third approach is based on the real-life problems, the cognitive base of which is included in the appropriate disciplines; the fourth approach is specified by the necessity of working on knowledge and skills on the material, which is significant for their future profession.

According to our research logics, we have defined professional situations in which future socio-cultural activity managers can be and how we can consider while situational tasks designing. Among main situations, in the frames of which future specialists' competence should be formed, we would like to point out the following ones:

1) organization of work (selection and placement of personnel, tasks delivering among departments or staff, development of entertainment industry, organization of work with mass media, organization of cultural events, organization of work of creative laboratories, workshops, creative studios, schools, centers of esthetic upbringing and creativity, etc.);

2) setting up cooperation in the professional sphere (discussing and own position defending, using verbal and non-verbal communication, adapting own working style to partner's style, adjusting own actions to colleagues ones, creating emotionally comfortable conditions for joint activity, etc.);

3) scientific research with the aim of popularization of socio-cultural sphere (organization, conducting and participating in scientific conferences and projects);

4) managing socio-cultural sphere (designing strategical and current aims and tasks of socio-cultural development, regulation of staff activity, demand management on products of cultural industry, etc.);

5) the situation of motivation (stimulation of performers for the execution of planned actions and achievement of goals);

6) marketing activity (research of competitive environment, designing organization style, financial resources involvement on project realization) and others.

It is also worth pointing out that while selecting material in the process of situational tasks designing, a teacher should follow principles, in particular: the situational task has to reflect the specifics of the professional activity sphere; tasks must be up-to-date; there must be a real situation in the tasks, which stimulates different emotions demonstration (empathy, surprise, joy, anger, etc.); the researched problem must be clear to the student; situational tasks solving must be aimed at identifying of the level of material knowledge and opportunity of its optimal usage in the process of the task performance; implementation of different means of situational tasks solving (some variants of answers, the list of right and wrong actions, right actions building in the order of importance, tasks without examples of right actions responses, answers on the cards, giving characteristics and analysis of the presented situation, etc.) (Reshetnyak, 2016, p. 24). Thus, the main idea of situational tasks is creating a highly informative environment, which stimulates the creative and reflexive activity of future specialists (particularly socio-cultural activity managers).

3.5. Recommended situational tasks

In the result of scientists' works analysis, we have designed situational tasks for the professional training of future socio-cultural activity managers, which were mainly created according to the structure mentioned above, including the name, the situation, personally important cognitive task, information from the task, types of situational tasks (*Table 1*).

Different approaches concerning future socio-cultural activity managers' training with situational tasks usage have been described in scientific sources. In addition, the real practice of teachers' work proposes even more models. We would like to analyze recommendations, presented by a doctor of education V. Liubarets (2019), in particular:

1) necessary connection with the specific students' activity – it is worth solving problematic situations, during which students master abilities and skills of performing educational-manufacturing works; situational task must be close to the professional work and reflect manufacturing process of socio-cultural activity; it is worth solving situational tasks on all stages of the practical lesson and creating and solving situational tasks individually with the maximal approach to manufacturing (pp. 254-256);

2) educational material content analysis – it is necessary to specify knowledge and skills of the future specialists on the practical lesson topic, to highlight central notions and labor methods as for students’ acquisition of the educational material, to identify novelty level and educational information difficulties, to determine educational material teaching logic and controversial information facts, to fix introduced situational task type, to design working methods during the situational task solving, to prepare educational means and didactic provision of a practical lesson (pp. 259-260);

3) educational material content analysis – it is necessary to specify knowledge and skills of the future specialists on the practical lesson topic, to highlight central notions and labor methods as for students’ acquisition of the educational material, to identify novelty level and educational information difficulties, to determine educational material teaching logic and controversial information facts, to fix introduced situational task type, to design working methods during the situational task solving, to prepare educational means and didactic provision of a practical lesson (pp. 259-260);

4) correct selection of the actual plots from the students’ practice and experience – to describe situations according to the subject content and methods, to formulate the problem of socio-cultural character clearly, to motivate students for the intellectual activity, to take into consideration students’ knowledge level and their creative opportunities concerning socio-cultural activity, to give necessary instructions for situational tasks solving (p. 260).

Table 1. Examples of situational tasks for the professional training of future socio-cultural activity managers

Title	Situation	Cognitive task	Information from the task
1	2	3	4
My work	You have to apply for a job. For this, you need to provide all the necessary documents to the employer concerning your education, experience in management, personal qualities, interests, etc.	To write a CV	Abilities to fill in the forms in Ukrainian and the foreign language, indicating the name, surname, the date and place of work, sex, occupation, hobbies, education, work experience, personal qualities, etc.

Extension of Table 1

1	2	3	4
<i>Situational tasks types: task “on data analysis”, “example tasks”, task “on abilities and skills formation”, and task “on justification”</i>			
Staff selection	You need a new employee in your event company. You are looking for a suitable candidate by placing an advertisement concerning a vacancy in the newspaper or on the Internet	To write an advertisement in the newspaper or on the Internet concerning a vacancy of a PR-manager	Abilities to define the basis of an exact vacancy and demands to the employee and to explain this in the right language
<i>Situational tasks types: task “on the mobile decision”, “example tasks”, task “on abilities and skills formation”, task “on information search”, task “on justification”</i>			
Celebrities of socio-cultural sphere	You were asked to participate in the educational-scientific. You have to express your thoughts concerning entertainment industry development	To prepare a report about the most famous achievement in the entertainment industry	Abilities to find the necessary information from different sources, to analyze it, synthesize, regulate and present it in Ukrainian and in a foreign language
<i>Situational tasks types: task “on data analysis”, “example tasks”, task “on abilities and skills formation”, task “on information search”, task “on algorithm production”, task “on foresight”</i>			
Informational etiquette	With the purpose of relationships building with foreign partners, professional communication with them with the help of the Internet resources, you are asked to prepare a proposition letter concerning business cooperation	To prepare a proposition letter concerning business cooperation	Skills to use Internet technologies in professional purposes, to communicate competently through documentation, to express thoughts in a foreign language, to use abbreviations relevantly, to stick to punctuation rules while writing a proposition letter

Extension of Table 1

1	2	3	4
<i>Situational tasks types:</i> task “on decision choice”, task “on data analysis”, task “on justification”, task “on abilities and skills formation”, task “on foresight”, task “on complication”			
Organization of the event	You are an employee (creative director) of the Palace of Culture. Engineering-building company “Architect” turned to you to conduct a professional holiday event for them	To prepare a scenario of the event	Abilities to define peculiarities of architect profession, peculiarities of scenario writing, its types and structure, to define dramatic (compositional) scenario construction
<i>Situational tasks types:</i> task “on data analysis”, “example tasks”, task “on abilities and skills formation”, task “on the decision taken analysis”, task “on information search”, task “on algorithm production”, task “on foresight”			
Touristic-excursion route	The scientific-creative expedition of socio-cultural activity managers is held in your city. You were asked to prepare individual business touristic-excursion route around the city	To prepare individual business touristic-excursion route around the city on the exact subject	Abilities to define peculiarities of touristic-excursion route and its types, to choose objects to show and present them, to give a client full information concerning excursion route
<i>Situational tasks types:</i> task “on decision choice”, task “on data analysis”, task “on abilities and skills formation”, task “on discussion solution”, task “on information search”, task “on algorithm production”			
Scientific research	You are preparing a scientific project in the socio-cultural activity sphere in a particular area. For this purpose, you need to collect information on this subject	To carry out socio-cultural diagnostics of this area	Abilities to analyze information on the following parameters: territory and its peculiarities; scientific and educational institutions, health protection organizations, social protection institutions, sport, culture, and art organizations
<i>Situational tasks types:</i> task “on data analysis”, task “on abilities and skills formation”, task “on information search”, task “on algorithm production”			

Source: own development

Thus, situational task implementation in the educational process contributes to students' striving to unexpected situations solving, cognitive abilities, analytical and logical thinking that stimulates individual research actions. Comparing to other educational tasks in the professional training of socio-cultural activity managers, situational tasks advantage is in students' cognitive activity stimulation at the moment of their solving, deliberate implementation of the obtained knowledge, culture development of student's scientific language, which will be a part of a modern socio-cultural activity manager profile.

4. Conclusions

The results of the conducted research let us define the importance of situational tasks usage in the professional training of future socio-cultural activity managers and come to the following conclusions:

1. The retrospective method implementation let us define key moments in the history of situational tasks emerging and development, among which: designing of situational tasks as a particular educational form by J. Dewey in 1859-1952; bringing the educational process to the practical activity by J. Dewey; project method creation by W. Kilpatrick; implementation of the situational tasks while teaching specific disciplines in the USA and other countries.

2. The terminological analysis results of the key notions of the Ukrainian and foreign scientists' research and literature allowed us to regulate the conceptual-terminological apparatus of the research. The notion "situational task" was specified, defined as an educational task, with the help of which future managers of socio-cultural activity can see themselves in the role of employees and get minimal experience in finding reasonable solutions. Such an approach will help students to feel confident in similar real situations.

3. We consider the main types of situational tasks as the following ones: "on the mobile decision", "on decision choice", "on data analysis", "example tasks", "on justification", "on abilities and skills formation", "on argumentative decision", "on decision taken analysis", "on information search", "on complication", "on algorithm production" and "on foresight". We have proved that it is worth using all presented situational tasks during socio-cultural activity managers' professional training.

4. The typical structure of the situational task has to include the name, situation, personally significant cognitive task, and information on the task. In particular, we have introduced situational tasks for the professional training of the future socio-cultural activity managers, designed according to the presented structure.

5. The content of situational tasks is in-group discussion and in analyzing different professionally-oriented situations. We have defined professional situations in which future socio-cultural activity managers can be and how we can consider while situational tasks' designing, particularly: organization of work, setting up cooperation in the professional sphere, scientific research, managing socio-cultural sphere, the situation of motivation, marketing activity.

Thus, unlike, for example, tests and traditional questions, situational tasks have not only knowledge controlling function, but educational element and development of thinking of future socio-cultural activity managers. These tasks contain many professional terms, specific language clichés, professional toolbox usage, and others, which undoubtedly help students make definite associative connections and enhance educational material remembering quality. While answering traditional questions or doing tasks, a student performs a role of an “executor”. There is an opposite position while solving a situational task. In this case, a student has to think over; there is an element of creativity, a discussion, quick problems solving skills forming, choosing the right decision among various variants, etc.

The scientific novelty. The scientific novelty of obtained scientific results lies in the specification of the concept “situational task”, which we consider as an educational task, with the help of which future managers of socio-cultural activity can see themselves in the role of employees and get minimal experience in finding reasonable solutions from a position of professional competence; in the systematization of situational task structure in the professional education of future socio-cultural activity managers, which includes the name, situation, personally significant cognitive task, and information on the task; in the analysis of the situational tasks' content and the introduction of professional situations for the education of socio-cultural managers.

The significance of the study. The practical significance is in the possibility of the obtained results usage in the educational process of the higher institutions. At the same time, respective positions can be used by socio-cultural sphere teachers and other specialties taking into account the specifics of their activity.

Prospects for further research. The perspective for future scientific research is in designing and experimental justification of the methodology of future socio-cultural activity managers' professional training.

Acknowledgement

This publication was prepared under the scientific research theme of the Department of Psychology, Political Science and Socio-Cultural Technologies of the Sumy State University in the context of the topic “Interdisciplinary Research of the Modern Society Development Aspects” (Project No. 01164007770).

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Information about the Authors:

Olga Boyko, Professor, DSc, Sumy State University, 2, Rimsky-Korsakov St., Sumy 40007, Ukraine; e-mail: boykoolga0204@ukr.net; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8484-6625> (corresponding author)

Anna Jeremus-Lewandowska, Professor, PhD, Ignacy Jan Paderewski Academy of Music in Poznan, Poznan, Poland; e-mail: annajeremus@poczta.onet.pl; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3278-3818>

Larysa Otroshchenko, Assoc. Professor, PhD, Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine; e-mail: l.otroshchenko@uabs.sumdu.edu.ua; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2333-333X>

Tatiana Povalii, Senior Lecturer, PhD, Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine; e-mail: tatianapovaliy@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5821-9775>

Yuliia Baidak, Assoc. Professor, PhD, Sumy Regional Institute Postgraduate Pedagogical Education, Sumy, Ukraine; e-mail: yulya.baidak@ukr.net; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8466-6904>